

Workshop on Data Collection and Operationalization of Film Festival Categories

27-28 May 2021

Skadi Loist & Zhenya Samoilova

[Film Circulation](#) Project (2017-2021)
Film University Babelsberg KONRAD WOLF

Abstract: The main goal of this workshop is to discuss approaches to delineating relevant characteristics of a film festival within the context of an empirical quantitative study. Most importantly, the workshop aims to highlight possible links and gaps between theoretical concepts and empirical realities. The paper stems from the project “Film Circulation in the International Festival Network and the Influence on Global Film Culture” funded by the German Ministry of Education and Research¹ that focuses on festival runs of a diverse sample of 10.502 films. Existing approaches to collecting data on film festivals often include in-depth research and the curation of festival lists with a specific thematic or geographical focus and, therefore, of an easily manageable size. In contrast, the Circulation project needs to handle a large number of festivals of various geographical and thematic clusters. Therefore, a comprehensive theoretical approach is required that needs to be reconciled with empirical challenges of data collection.

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Workshop Program

Day 1: Thursday, 27 May 2021, 17:00-19:00 CET

as part of the **Film Festival Research Seminar series**

<https://us02web.zoom.us/j/83280819863?pwd=VzlxWUM0anExelQ4a0cvZDlCMjJ1dz09>

Meeting ID: 832 8081 9863 | Access Code: 667413

Approaches to Film Festival Categorization: Existing Projects & Data Sets

How do existing theoretical models and our research questions translate into forms of operationalization in empirical research? What are the questions for analysis in the various projects? How can we define: impact, hierarchies and their effects? How can we objectively, empirically measure the "impact" / reach / hierarchy factors?

In tackling these questions we want to learn from existing data sets and projects. What are the challenges?

Input presentations

1) Why We Operationalize

Ann Vogel (HU Berlin)

Vogel received her Ph.D. from the University of Washington and holds three Master-level degrees: in sociology from the University of Amsterdam, in social work/social administration and education science from the Technical University of Berlin, and in university and science management from the German University of Administrative Sciences at Speyer. Her research works include a doctoral thesis on the historical rise of philanthropic fundraising for US higher education, a monograph manuscript on the function of festival curations in aesthetic capitalism, and articles in organizational and institutional analysis covering her key areas, including civil society, higher education, philanthropy, work and occupations as well as socioeconomic development and remittance migration. Vogel has taught sociology, methods, and social theory at universities around the world, including mentoring international students in interdisciplinary schools. Vogel is a practicing sociologist but for state-licensing reasons currently on a four-year social work practice term in a refugee consultancy in Germany, as she prepares to combine sociology and social work into a new area of teaching.

2) What counts as a "festival"? Categorising small film festivals in Chile

Maria Paz Peirano (Universidad de Chile)

María Paz Peirano is an Assistant Professor in Film and Cultural Studies at Universidad de Chile, with a PhD in Social Anthropology from the University of Kent. Her research involves an ethnographic approach to film as social practice, focusing on contemporary Chilean cinema, film festivals, and the development of Chilean film cultures. She is co-editor of the volume *Film Festivals and Anthropology* (Cambridge Scholars 2017) and co-creator of www.festivalesdecine.cl. She was the lead researcher of "Film festivals: exhibition and circulation of Chilean cinema", which mapped Chilean film festivals, and of "Film Festivals, educative experiences and the expansion of the Chilean field", looking at festivals' training hubs and audience development. She was part of the team of "Historic billboard: Film exhibition and reception in Santiago between 1918 and 1969" and she is currently the lead researcher of "Chilean film audiences: film culture, cinephilia and education" (FONDECYT 1211594).

3) Delimiting the Boundaries: For a Taxonomy of Film Festivals in the Basque context

Aida Vallejo (UPV/EHU)

Aida Vallejo is a film historian and social anthropologist. Associate Professor at University of the Basque Country (UPV/EHU) She holds a PhD in History of Cinema by Autonomous University of Madrid with a study of documentary film festivals in Europe, and a MA on theory and practice of documentary film by Autonomous University of Barcelona. Aida is the founder and coordinator of the Documentary Work-group of the European Network for Cinema and Media Studies (NECS). She has published extensively on documentary and film festivals, narratology and ethnography of the media, and with María Paz Peirano has co-edited *Film Festivals and Anthropology*. Her two co-edited collections *Documentary Film Festivals Vol 1* and *Vol 2* have been published by Palgrave MacMillan's Framing Film Festivals series. She is principal investigator of ikerFESTS, a research project to map the Basque film festival landscape, funded by University of the Basque Country.

4) Film festival research in small and precarious cinemas: Central American film festivals

Jasper Vanhaelemeesch (Antwerp)

Jasper Vanhaelemeesch (Belgium, 1991) obtained his doctoral degree in Film Studies and Visual Culture at the University of Antwerp's Visual and Digital Cultures Research Center (ViDi) in April 2021. Jasper obtained his bachelor's degree in Linguistics and Literature (English-Spanish) at KU Leuven in 2012, a master's degree in Western Literature in 2013 and an advanced master's degree in Cultures and Development Studies in 2015, both at KU Leuven. In May 2016, he started as a PhD researcher on the Vandebunder Baillet Latour chair for Film Studies and Visual Culture under the supervision of Prof. Dr. Philippe Meers (University of Antwerp). From 2017 until 2019, Jasper performed a total of five months of fieldwork at film festivals in Central America and Cuba, supported by a travel grant from the Research Foundation - Flanders (FWO). Parts of his doctoral research have been published in international peer-reviewed journals such as *Studies in Spanish and Latin American Cinemas*, *NECSUS: European Journal of Media Studies*, *Transnational Screens* and *Comunicación y medios*.

Day 2: Friday, 28 May 2021 17:00-20:00h CET

<https://us02web.zoom.us/j/86185376099?pwd=QUVFcWVNRnY5R2NFRjhXSfhWbWNIZz09>

Meeting-ID: 861 8537 6099 | Kenncode: 602631

17:00-17:20 CET Introduction to Workshop & Operationalization in the Circulation Project

How do we negotiate between data-driven research approaches vs. theory-driven approaches in film festival studies? How does (un)availability of data impact our research and theorizing (That's what we have vs. that's what we want to know)? Which questions can be answered by data (that we have)? Brief input based on the pre-circulated paper on questions of Operationalization
What are our research objectives? Which data sources and data are available? How can we make use of existing categorizations?

17:20-18:00 CET Question / Discussion Block 1: How does (Film) Theory translate into Empirical Festival Research

Challenges and limitations in categorizing festivals using existing characteristics such as genre & film types (Horror film festivals, short film or documentary), production contexts (independent film) or audience & community contexts (queer film festivals).

18:10-19:00 CET Question / Discussion Block 2: Operationalizing Industry Knowledge

How can seemingly "self-evident" industry (insider) experience and expert knowledge be translated into neutral, objective characteristics? E.g. how do we know that Sundance, Oberhausen and Sheffield [or "xxx"] are relevant festivals for independent, short or documentary films and how can this relevance or importance be operationalized?

19:10-20:00 CET Question / Discussion Block 3: Tackling nitty gritty details: Variables, data quality, missing data?

Which features and variables are collected and analyzed in film festival research? How do we deal with temporally specific data in a very dynamic field? How do we deal with retrospective evaluation of past events? What if for a specific edition no data can be found? How to account for collected data for future use?

Working Paper

Data Collection and Operationalization of Film Festival Categories

Skadi Loist & Zhenya Samoilova

1. Introduction: Data and Metrics for Film Festivals

There is an abundance of several thousand film festivals in operation. The growth of the film festival sector especially since the 1980s has led to increased interest in understanding and systematization of festivals. With the growing field, the number of involved stakeholders has grown. Public cultural funders and sponsors, film industry professionals such as filmmakers, producers and distributors working with festivals, and local politicians are just some of the interested parties. This festival landscape is increasingly captured in data, measured, and mapped. However, these data and metrics follow very specific logics, oftentimes generated internally by or for funders and seldom transparent or available to researchers. As an undirected, not centrally organized or controlled field (Iordanova 2009) it is hard to get a standardized overview.

In the last decade, a number of research projects have attempted to map the film festival landscape, but usually stayed within specific national or regional boundaries in these attempts. This is most likely a result of nationally oriented funding structures both for cultural and film funding as well as research funding. Various studies have attempted to give a comprehensive overview of the festival landscapes for France (Taillibert 2009), Austria (Zachar/Paul 2016), the Netherlands (van Vliet 2018; Baptist 2018), Germany (Krainhöfer 2018), Chile (Peirano 2016, Peirano/González Itier 2018), and the Basque Country (Vallejo 2019). Within the workshop we aim to draw on the expertise developed in these projects.

One of the questions arising from such an attempt is how exactly to define a film festival. How do you differentiate a film festival from a film series? How can we distinguish the different kinds and types of festivals? What would be the key parameters for their categorizations? Possible characteristics that have been proposed are: 1) *size* of the festivals, measured through number of films shown, number of venues, duration and frequency of the event, visitor counts, organization budget; 2) *outreach* as visible in location or target audience, especially for community-based festivals, and 3) *film selection* in terms of type, length, genre or further curatorial markers (cf. Reichel-Heldt 2007, 23-24; de Valck/Loist 2009; de Valck 2016, 2-3; Baptist 2018, 5). The main question here is how these characteristics can be operationalized and measured empirically without having a notable share of missing data. We will come back to the discussion of specific parameters below.

Within the emerging field of “film festival studies” (De Valck/Loist 2009) a few attempts of systematization have been made that draw on theoretical discussions within film studies, such as the conceptions of film types, genres and style which inform the discussion of curation and film selection. Similarly, recent discussions on transnational and global (art) cinema and their (uneven) circulation inform how film festival have been discussed, as champions of world cinema as well as gatekeepers for “festival films”.

The research project “Film Circulation in the International Festival Network and the Influence on Global Film Culture” is drawing on all of these sources and aims to reconcile the theoretical knowledge with necessities of empirical methodological work as it attempts to scale up and move from individual case-studies to a global understanding of the festival network and utilize a big cultural data / digital humanities approach.

2. Theoretical approaches to classification of film festivals

One main issue that has been highlighted from a critical humanities/film studies perspective is the relationships of festivals within the vast festival landscape, which is discussed as a *network* with certain nodes (Elsaesser 2005, de Valck 2007) or as loose collection of festivals with unclear connection as a circuit that lacks governance and a coordinating structure to be discussed as distribution chain (Iordanova 2009, 24). It seems undisputed though that the festival landscape is hierarchically structured and stratified. There are a number of conceptual dimensions here: 1) *temporal* considerations connected to premiere logics theorized as a ‘*calendar*’, 2) there are (*geo*)-*spatial* considerations connected to the host city and film industry locations, which have also been scrutinized and criticized for creating unequal power structures and even neocolonial tendencies for the larger global film market (e.g. Ross 2011, Stringer 2016), and 3) a differentiation along main stakeholders as differentiated between *industry* vs. *audience* relationship (Peranson 2009).

The festival landscape is conceptualized as a connected network that has developed specific routes or circuits. In industry jargon the ‘circuit’ often is used to refer to the top-tier festival with major market influence, oftentimes equivalent to the FIAPF-accredited A-list festival and/or festivals with a market attached. With an interest in specific films and film genres, the image of parallel circuits or sub-circuits has been established (Iordanova 2009, Vallejo 2012, 2014; Loist/Zielinski 2012; Loist 2014/2018, 2016). Some of these subcircuits are based on the classification of festivals, by genre such as documentary and short film festivals, or by community connection, such as LGBT*Q, women’s or Jewish film festivals.

These routes or circuits within the festival landscape work on different levels of connection. One, is the route a *film* takes from festival to festival, creating a festival run of consecutive screenings. [This leads to a discussion of the festival network as an “alternative distribution system”, a discussion for which the industrial mechanisms and models of exhibition vs. distribution need to be further interrogated. This cannot be discussed in this workshop.] Two, is the route or network created by *film professionals* connected through various activities. There is film talent traveling with their films on the festival run as part of the exhibition and promotion of films (Vallejo 2015; Peirano 2017). However, festivals are not only exhibition sites, but have long become meeting places for the industry, where different stakeholders meet to pitch and develop future projects. Third, through the competition and collaboration between festivals, ideas, *programs* and *lab formats* also spread through the network, creating a circuit of project incubators and co-production markets (de Valck 2013; Vallejo 2017; Falicov 2016). In this way, festivals do not only influence film exhibition and distribution through their selection and showcasing of films, but they have an effect on film production, which feeds back into the festival circuit, when these new films developed on the circuit are then premiered and presented on the festival circuit. At the same time, the festival landscape and circuit is constantly re-developing its mechanisms and programs.

Taking these various elements into account, in her discussion of the functioning of festivals in their support of art cinema, Marijke de Valck (2014) has offered one preliminary way to describe the stratification of festivals and offered a model of a tier system, which is mainly based on their market logic within the film and distribution industry. In this, she uses a core-periphery model to differentiate between what Mark Peranson has termed “business festivals” (2009). She discusses the top-tier festivals as

the first tier hold the core power grid of the festival circuit: They organize the handful of markets that really matter internationally, and they host the world’s most prestigious competitions. Films from first tier competitions typically embark on a festival tour of second and third tiers, as well as audience festivals after their well-covered world premier at a first tier festival. Examples of first tier festivals are Cannes, Venice, Berlin, Toronto, Hong Kong and Busan. (De Valck 2014: 47)

Second-tier business festivals “are located outside the core, but they offer specialized services that significantly feed back into the festival core services such as a leading co-production market and/or fund (IFFR, Torino), a vibrant independent scene (Sundance, Tribeca) or cutting edge special programmes (Vienna).” (de Valck 2014: 47-48) While third-tier business festivals are described to have limited reach to the global circuit, but significant impact in country or region, “that act as the major meeting site for local professionals, but do not initiate developments that cause ripples substantial enough to affect the first tier core” (de Valck 2014: 48).

This is a very useful distinction when looking at hierarchies and market force or what I would call “circulation power” of film festivals (Loist 2020). However, one of the main arguments behind the Film Circulation project is that the vast amount of festivals within the film festival landscape is not accounted for and theorized when we only look at the top-crop of general programmed business festivals, i.e. what are usually generically called the “[host city] international film festival”. The vast number of festivals on the parallel circuits does not come into view even though they are an integral part of the network and essential for the exhibition especially of smaller, specialized arthouse film (Loist 2016, 2014). For the LGBT*Q sector this are about 230 festivals alone, 170+ Jewish film festivals are listed etc. (Loist 2013).

In order to try and also account for these festivals and place them within a model of a cohesive network, I have proposed to extend the tier-system to include all festivals. To achieve this, two stratified pyramids – which also in form represent the larger number of smaller festivals than the very narrow top level of top-tier festivals – are merged (see also Graph 1 and Table 1). While the first pyramid represents the three tiers of festivals following the industry logic (de Valck 2014) and the second includes also festivals that within the larger industry logic are of lesser importance, but within their thematic segments hold significant positions, for instance as the top-tier festivals within the circuit of documentary festivals or LGBT*Q festivals. This model aims to integrate an industry-driven tier system, which is also largely based in external classification, such as FIAPF accreditation or industry listing, with the knowledge of specialized sub-circuits that are rather operating on audience-driven logics.

Figure 1: inclusive model of festival tiers

The goal is to find a system that can ideally account for the broad variety of festivals in the field, of which the majority does not fit the tight industry-categorization system (see Table 1 below). For our purposes here, and the Circulation research project in more general, the idea is to also capture the worth of small festivals for exhibition/distribution of films on the network.

Table 1. Tier system of film festival circuit

Approximate stratum	Festival hierarchy*	Characteristics	Organizational chain value and approximate festival circuit position	Examples
1	First-tier business festivals	Most prestigious global competitions; markets with global reach; most world premieres	Core	Festivals of Cannes, Venice, Berlin, Toronto, Hong Kong, Busan
2	Second-tier business festivals	Prestigious, specialized services, leading co-production markets and/or funds, state-of-the art independent cinema, cutting-edge special programming	Closer to core	Festivals of Edinburgh, Rotterdam, Sundance Torino, Tribeca, Vienna; Clermont-Ferrand Short Film Festival, International Documentary Film Festival Amsterdam, International Short Film Festival Oberhausen
3	Third tier business festivals	Leading events in country and/or region; major meeting sites for local/national professionals	Closer to periphery	Filmfest Hamburg, Seattle International Film Festival, Filmfest München, Frameline, Outfest, Frauenfilmfestival Dortmund Köln, Leipzig DOX

4	First-tier audience festivals	Audience-oriented regional and local festivals, general or specialized program, local/regional community-orientation, small national festivals, genre and/or identity festivals, low or no industry presence	Semi-periphery	Jewish Film Festival of Hong Kong, ... QFF Hamburg, FilmKunstFest SN; Ophüls, Mannheim/Heidelberg, ...
5	Second-tier audience festivals	Exclusively audience, community-oriented events with local reach being limited local reach	Periphery	FiSH, QFF Rostock;

Following Minerva Campos-Rabadán's recent article on the inequalities within the international film sector (2020), the ranking of film festivals in a center-periphery logic would need to be reconsidered in an attempt to account for diverging perspectives and thus deal with Eurocentric or North-American centric discourses within the global film industry.

One of the main challenges of the festival categorization is to translate theoretical approaches into empirically measurable concepts. In order to empirically assess a given classification scheme, one first needs to measure assembling blocks such as e.g. location, specialization/focus, time (in order to measure sequencing), external accreditation/evaluation, as well as relevance/importance of a given festival. Collecting data on even such seemingly straightforward facts such as date, location, and focus (if there is any) of the festival is not always a trivial task. The biggest challenge is however to operationalize and collect data on impact and importance of a given festival in the circuit. Below, we provide an overview of dealing with these challenges within the Circulation project.

3. The Film Circulation Project: Studying Film Festivals with Various Data Sources

Despite the very large and further rising number of festivals, there is still very limited data available on the approximate number of festivals as well as on the distribution of festival features such as themes, foundation years, location, genre, etc. Most of the existing approaches to collecting data on film festivals include in-depth, qualitative, case-study based research and the compilation of separate festival lists centered around thematic or regional circuits (e.g., human rights festivals, LGBTQ+ festivals, etc.). These data are valuable, especially in methodological terms when the logic of research and selection is known and the sources transparent, i.e. when a researcher involved in the process is known and can be approached (e.g. Baptist 2018; van Vliet 2018; Loist 2018b; Colta 2019). However, these data resources are limited when dealing with research questions about complex temporal and spatial festival circulation patterns of a large and diverse sample of films.

The Circulation project studies the film movements, so-called festival runs, of 10.502 films on the festival network. The project has collected data on all of the reported festivals, where these films participated. The sample of films was selected from seven years of programs (2011-2017) of six festivals. The six festivals were chosen, so that the breadth of the festival network and diversity of films can be taken into account. Therefore, the first three festivals were chosen

from the first tier of industry festivals: *The Berlin International Film Festival (Berlinale)*, *the Festival de Cannes*, and *the Toronto International Film Festival (TIFF)*. Other films were selected from three third-tier business festival from parallel circuits with a special focus (e.g. documentary film, short film and queer cinema): *the International Documentary Film Festival Amsterdam (IDFA)*, *Clermont-Ferrand* as the leading short film festival with a film market located in France, and *Frameline* as the oldest queer film festival in San Francisco. The collection of festival screenings within the festival runs for this large and diverse sample of films results in the collection of thousands of highly diverse film festivals that need to be categorized.

To collect data on the festival run and its relation to other exhibition windows, the project resorts to several data sources. One of the sources is a web-based survey (the questionnaire Samoilova/Loist 2019 can be accessed [here](#)). Experience from a pilot study on film circulation by Skadi Loist and Ann Vogel (2014) has shown that many filmmakers collect data on the festival runs of their films. Therefore, a survey is the best way to get an almost complete picture of the festival runs. Yet, the main problem of surveys (especially web-based surveys) is low response rates (Groves 2011). The latter does not automatically affect the representativeness of a sample, but variable-specific nonresponse bias (i.e. when nonresponding units differ from responding units on a certain quality in a systematic way) can occur and, hence, should be empirically examined (Callegaro 2015). The first round of the survey (films from the festivals of the 2013 programs) indicated, that filmmakers sampled from the programs of Cannes and TIFF are very difficult to approach via a web survey – hence the survey sample is dominated by films shown at smaller festivals. In addition, 17 percent of respondents evaluated their festival data as incomplete and nine percent were not sure, whether the festival data they provided were complete or not (Loist/Samoilova 2020).

The second data source of the festival runs constitutes the International Movie Database (IMDb). IMDb is the most comprehensive, yet commercially operated (currently owned by Amazon) crowdsourcing-based film database. While the quality of the IMDb data makes it difficult to use it for historical research, it remains an empirical question to what extent it can be used to collect data on festival and other types of distribution of films. The IMDb data contribution guidelines treat festivals as a type of release (along with theatrical and TV releases). We were able to identify and link 87 percent of the films in our sample to the IMDb dataset. Unlike the survey sample, in the IMDb sample, films screened at the first-tier festivals (TIFF, Cannes, and Berlinale) were much more prevalent than those from smaller specialized festivals (IDFA, Clermont-Ferrand, Frameline). In this context IMDb is a good addition to surveys, as filmmakers, production and sales companies of more prominent films are much more difficult to approach via a survey. While neither of the sources includes an exhaustive list of festivals where films were shown, both of them provide a fuller picture than each of them separately.

4. Festival Characteristics

According to the survey and IMDb data sources, the first sample of 1.727 films of the 2013 festival season (the rest of the 2011-2017 sample are currently being analyzed) are related to 2.232 unique film festivals. To analyze these data further, the festivals had to be categorized based on their relevant features. While there have been some attempts to introduce a comprehensive list of festival features, in our project we primarily focus on the features relevant for the research questions (to find larger scale patterns of film circulation on the

festival circuit), and theoretical concepts (e.g. on hierarchies of festivals, transnational/global cinema) described in section 1 (see Figure 2). Therefore, the characteristics offered here are by no means exhaustive, but are the result of temporal and data access constraints and tailored towards a specific focus. The chosen features can be divided into the following groups: general characteristics, temporal characteristics, geographical characteristics, information on used data sources and search on the web, external evaluation, and characteristics of various specializations (if there are any).

In order to be able to answer key questions about complex relationships of film circulation patterns to parameters such as premiere status of the festivals, ranking and hierarchical positioning of the festivals within the festival network, i.e. their circulation power (Loist 2020), which have an impact of the path a film travels, *the goal is to categorize the festivals according to empirical and theoretical characteristics*. Currently we are tackling two main questions:

1) *How do we arrive at a meaningful ranking of all festivals within the five-tier model outlined above, especially when the high number of festivals in our research sample make it impossible to individually research each festival in depth. What are the empirical data characteristics which allow us to put festivals into those tiers?*

2) *How can we divide the overall festival network into meaningful subcircuits or specialization categories, which allow us to analyze the festival runs for specific film types and within parallel circuits?* (See the diagram arm of festival focus in Figure 2, and the section on Specialization/Focus below).

Figure 2: Overview of festival characteristics developed and used within the project.

General characteristics

General characteristics include names and assigned ID of a given festival.

Table 2. General characteristics

<i>Characteristics name</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Open questions</i>
festival ID	Each unique festival is assigned a unique ID. If a festival changes its name or get merged with other festivals it is assigned a new ID.	Some festivals are organized under one umbrella but in various locations. From which point shall we treat them as one unique festival in multiple locations or as different festivals? Example: Human Rights Watch Festival that is held in more than 20 countries (https://ff.hrw.org/about)
name the festival	Name of a festival as it was entered in the first data source used.	
alternative names of the festival	Other names that become known during work with other sources.	

Temporal characteristics

Temporal characteristics include the time of the festival screening (relevant to a specific film) and the life course of the festival itself.

Table 3. Temporal characteristics

<i>Characteristics name</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Examples</i>
year of the festival	Year in which a film was screened at a given festival was collected via survey or IMDb. If the data were missing, they were researched in the festival programs (at the film level).	
months of the festival	Where possible, data on the month of the festival was collected via the survey or IMDb. In the case of missing data, student assistants searched for the data on the web, the primary source constituted the festival website (if another source was used, it was marked by the coder). Months of the festival are specific to the year, since in some cases months vary throughout years.	
foundation year of the festival	These data were researched on the web, the primary source constituted the festival website (if another source was used, it was marked by the coder). Foundation year is an approximation, as in some cases (depending on what festival writes about itself or other sources provide) it constitutes the first edition of the festival and in other cases 1-2 years before that, when organization begins.	
change of the festival	If research showed that a given festival changed its name, it is marked by entering a year when the change	Planete+ Doc Film Festival (founded in

	happens and a new name (with a new festival ID) is documented. However, due to the time limit, it is impossible to research the entire life course of each festival.	Warsaw in 2004) was changed in 2015 to Docs Against Gravity Film Festival.
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Geographical characteristics

Geographic characteristics indicate physical location of the festival and reflect some aspects of festivals' programming. For the categorization of festivals according to their programming focus – national, regional and transnational – we have adapted the definitions developed for the FFRN bibliography (de Valck/Loist 2009: 198; Loist/de Valck 2019)

Table 4. Geographical characteristics

<i>Characteristics name</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Examples</i>	<i>Open questions</i>
country location	Where possible, data on country location of a given festival was collected via the survey or IMDb. In the case of missing data, student assistants searched for the data on the web. The primary source constituted the festival website (if another source was used, it was marked accordingly). We also document, if a festival has several locations.		
city location	Where possible, data on city location of the festival was collected via the survey (these data are rarely available on IMDb). In the case of missing data, student assistants searched for the data on the web, the primary source constituted the festival website (if another source was used, it was marked accordingly). We also document, if a festival has several locations.		
national festival	Festivals that exclusively show films from a certain national context and are relevant to that national film industry.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Solothurner Filmtage</i> - <i>Dutch Film Festival in the Netherlands</i> - <i>Kinotavr film festival in Russia</i> - <i>Cnex documentary film festival in China</i> - <i>Festival de Cinema de Tres Passos in Brazil</i> 	
regional festival	Festivals that focus on films from a specific geographical or political region or films in the same language that are based in and relevant to that same region.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>The Americas film festival in the USA</i> - <i>Commonwealth Film Festival in the UK</i> - <i>Asia-Pacific Film Festival in China</i> 	

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Luxor African International Film Festival in Egypt</i> - <i>Gifu Asia Film Festival in Japan</i> 	
transnational festival	<p>Festivals that showcase films from a specific national or regional context, in a different country or region than the production countries. This can include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Film festivals showcasing a specific national cinematography outside of the country of origin ● Cultural diplomacy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>German FF in Australia</i> - <i>EU Film Days in Japan</i> - <i>Balkantagen in München</i> - <i>Israel Film Festival in Paris</i> - <i>Afrika filmfestival in Belgium</i> 	

Information on used data sources

This group of characteristics includes information about the search and the sources used.

Table 5. Information on used data sources

<i>Characteristics name</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Examples</i>	<i>Open questions</i>
festival no longer exists, is not identifiable, or cannot be found	<p>If the festival website (or its social media page) states it is stated that the festival no longer exists or information about the festival was not updated since 2017 (checked in 2021), we coded it as festival that no longer exists (if possible, the year of the last edition was stated). If the data provided in IMDb or survey (such as name of the festival, date and location) were not enough to distinguish a unique festival among several festivals with a similar name in the same location, it was coded as “not identifiable”. If no matching data were found on the web, the festival was coded as “cannot be found.”</p>		
website	Website of the festival, if one is available		
other sources used	If other data sources (not a website) were used as primary sources, it is coded accordingly, and the used data sources are documented.		

External evaluation

External evaluation includes a group of characteristics referring to rankings of external institutions such as International Federation of Film Producers Associations (FIAPF), the British Academy of Film and Television Arts (BAFTA), and the Academy of Motion Picture of Arts and Sciences (OSCARS).

Table 6. Information on external evaluation

Characteristics name	Description	Examples	Open questions
FIAPF	This variable signifies, if a festival is accredited in a given year by the FIAPF.		The FIAPF accreditation as well as OSCARS and BAFTA qualifying lists vary over the years (see Figures 3-5). Moreover, for some years, no reliable data sources can be found. The challenge is to account for this variation and missing data in the analysis.
Academy Awards (OSCARS)	Here it is stated, if a given festival is included in the list of OSCARS qualifying festivals in a given year.		
BAFTA	Here it is stated, if a given festival is included in the list of BAFTA qualifying festivals in a given year.		

Figure 3: Yearly variation of FIAPF accreditation for the period between 2006-2018. For years 2009, 2010, 2012, 2014, 2015, and 2017 data are missing.

Figure 4: Yearly variation of Academy Awards qualifying festivals for the period between 2014-2015. For years 2006-2013, and 2018 data are missing.

Figure 5: Yearly variation of BAFTA qualifying festivals for the period between 2014-2018. For years 2006-2013 data are missing. From 2016, the qualifying categories were changed to A and B-lists.

Specialization/Focus

The enormous growth of the film festival sector has also seen a differentiation of the festival landscape and development of specialized film festivals. There are various logics according to which these specializations can be grouped. For this we have started with the existing categorization of festivals that derived from the model developed for the Film Festival Research Network bibliography (de Valck/ Loist 2009, 204-210). This model was based on the existing *literature* on festivals, not necessarily the empirically existing festivals. Therefore, in our coding process for the Circulation process we have tried to refine and adapt this model.

Since the Circulation project is based on a research logic that views the festival network through the lens of the travelling films, the selection of categories is mainly based on elements that characterize films. Thus, the festivals are mainly categorized according to their programming (instead of, for instance, their organizational structure). One category is the distinction of film types (*Gattung*), such as festivals for long or short films, for feature films or documentaries, for animation or experimental films. Other qualities that distinguish a festival's specific programming profile might be the programming theme (films on history) or programming and reception contexts (activist festivals, community based festivals).

To identify specialization, we used the title of the festival and its self-description (on the website or social media channel used as an alternative to a website) as the primary source. In addition, availability of a special award in an indicated focus area can also be regarded as an additional cue for specialization. Yet, it is important to note, that not everything that is stated on festivals' web page can be literarily regarded as focus. Festivals create their web pages with a broad audience in mind. Thus, certain terms that might have a specific meaning in Film Studies or within film industry jargon might not be used in this regard. Therefore, they often use certain words (e.g., "independent film") or list various areas without implying a specialization. For example, if a festival description lists more than two categories of specialization, it probably has no specific focus at all. This creates potential methodological problems for coding of festivals if attempted by automated methods or by inexperienced coders. The categorization of some cases is difficult and requires some tacit knowledge. Therefore, a content discussion with an expert from a given area is an important step in the coding process.

Table 7: Information on focus/specialization

Characteristics name	Description	Examples	Open questions
Identity-based festivals			
Festivals that focus on the issue of identity categories in the sense of communities that are reflected in film content, audiences or/and support of film makers. The identity categories are often connected to activism and political movements, which have evolved into dedicated festivals. Oftentimes, festivals follow the logic of curating films "by, for and about" the respective community and are thus grounded in representation politics. Identified identities include:			
LGBT/Queer film festivals	LGBT/Queer identities / communities	- Tokyo International Lesbian & Gay Film Festival	
Women's film festivals	Women filmmakers, films by or about women	- Cairo International Women's Film Festival	
Jewish film festivals	Jewish identity / communities	- Jüdische Filmtage in München	
Black film festivals/Afric	Black/African-American identity / communities	- Toronto Black Film Festival	

an-American film festivals			
Latinx film festivals	Latinx identity / communities	- Sydney Latin American Film Festival	
Asian film festivals (also Asian-American, South East Asian)	Asian identities / communities	- Chicago South Asian Film Festival	
Indigenous film festivals	Indigenous identities / communities	- Message Sticks Indigenous Film Festival	
Other	Other ethnic, cultural, racial identities, including, but not limited to film festivals that could be classified as diasporic film festivals.	- Romani Film Festival Cacikano	In some cases, it is very difficult to identify (without specific expertise), if a given festival is focusing on identities or simply showcasing films from a certain region. For example: - African Film Festival Hamburg - India-Indian Film Festival of Melbourne - Afi Latin American
Genre-based festivals choose their films “according to what can be called ‘genre’ distinctions in the broadest sense” (de Valck/Loist 2009: 209).			
Film genre (often connected to existing fan cultures):			
Genre cinema	If a festival does not focus on one specific genre, but on genre cinema in general. Sometimes a festival can have an explicit statement on its website that the focus is genre cinema in general. In addition, this category can include festival that focus on genre with no strongly visible fan culture (e.g., crime, war, action)	- Strasbourg European Fantastic Film Festival - Outlier Film Festival in Canada - Black Bear filmfest in Poland - Night Visions Film Festival in Finland - Mile High Horror Film Festival in the USA	
Fantasy + Sci Fi + Horror + Thriller	A festival focuses on fantasy films, Science Fiction, and/or horror and thriller	- Athens International Sci-Fi & Fantasy Film Festival - Neuchatel International Fantastic Film Festival in Switzerland - Sitges International Fantastic Film Festival of Catalonia in Spain - Festival de Gerardmer in France - Dead by Dawn Horror Film Festival in the UK - Studio k horror festival in the Netherlands	
Comedy	A festival focuses on comedy films	- LA Comedy Festival in the USA	

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		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Old Town Taito International Comedy Film Festival in Japan - L'alpe D'huez International Comedy Film Festival in France 	
Porn and Erotic	A festival focuses on porn and erotic film	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Porny Days Film Art Festival in Switzerland 	This category is often linked to LGBTQ/Queer category.
Music and dance	A festival focuses on music and dance films	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cine Rock Festival Japan - Norient Musikfilm Festival in Switzerland - Immagini & Suoni del Mondo in Italy - In-Edit Chile - Dance for Camera, USA 	
Independent	The category “independent film” is a common term used within film industry and distribution/exhibition contexts. In some cases, “independent” also refers to the creation and historical development of a festival.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Indie Lisboa International Film Festival - Sundance Film Festival - International Film Festival Rotterdam - !f Istanbul International Independent Film Festival 	<p>Yet, the term is contested when trying to pin down on a clearcut definition. As a category that specifically makes sense within a North American production context, it is unclear how useful it is for film outside of the US.</p> <p>Example: Black Movie International Independent Film Festival in Geneve (https://blackmovie.ch/intedition/)</p> <p>It is important to note, that various festivals use the word “independent” in their description, without an explicit focus on independent film, while others focus on independent films without using the word directly in their description (e.g., Indie Lisboa)</p>
Underground (including trash)	A festival focuses on underground and trash films	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sydney Underground Film Festival - Chicago Underground Film Festival - Pineapple Underground Film Festival in Hong Kong - Mumia Underground World Animation Film Festival in Brazil - But Film Festival in the Netherlands 	
Film Type (Gattung) refers to festivals showcasing films „defined by stylistic or narrative features, such as animation, archival, documentary, ethnographic, experimental, fiction, or silent film.” (Loist/de Valck 2019):			
Animation film festivals	Festivals featuring primarily animation films	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Animated dreams in Estonia 	

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		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fest Anca International animation festival in Slovakia - France National Animation Film Festival - Seoul International Cartoon & Animation Festival (sicaf) - Tehran International Animation Festival 	
Archival film festivals (also includes retrospectives / “classics”, and silent film)	Festivals featuring primarily archival, retrospective, classics, and silent films	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lumiere Film Festival in France - One Queer Film Fest One National Archive in the USA - TCM Classic Film Festival in the USA - San Francisco Silent Film Festival - Silent Film Festival in Greece 	
Documentary film festivals	Festivals featuring primarily documentary films	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Hot Docs Canadian International Documentary Festival - Artdocfest Russian Open Documentary Film Festival - Budapest International Documentary Festival – BIDF - Bordocs Foro Documental in Mexico - IDFA – International Documentary Filmfestival Amsterdam 	
Experimental film festivals	Festivals featuring primarily experimental films	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - experimenta in india - anadoma experimental film & video festival in Germany - BIDEODROMO Internacional Experimental Film and Video Festival in Spain - Videoex International Experimental Film & Video Festival Zurich - Flexfest Florida 	
Ethnographic /Anthropological Film Festival	Festivals featuring primarily ethnographic and anthropological film	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ethnocineca Ethnographic and Documentary Filmfest Vienna - Paernu International Documentary and Anthropology Film Festival, Estonia 	
Short film festivals	Since most festivals show a range of films in different lengths, the most common distinction is that of short film festivals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Interfilm International Short Film Festival Berlin - Short Film Festival Leuven 	

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	(Loist/de Valck 2019). Short film, much like documentary film, follows different logics in exhibition and distribution.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ismailia International Film Festival for Documentary & Shorts, Egypt - Tehran international short film festival - Clermont Ferrand International Short Film Festival 	
Children and youth	Festivals showcasing films for children and youth	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Jerusalem International Film Festival for Children and Youth - Children Kinofest in the Ukraine - Seoul International Youth Film Festival - International Children's Film Festival Bangladesh - Cairo International Cinema and Arts Festival for Children 	
Student	Festivals with a focus on emerging student filmmakers or/and organized by students	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Festival Sehnsüchte, Potsdam - SCAD Savannah Film Festival, USA - Bangkok International Student Film Festival - Internationales Festival der Filmhochschulen München 	
Debut / Emerging talents / up-and-coming	Festivals with a focus on emerging talents in filmmaking.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Bogota Film Festival, Colombia - Cannes International Critics' Week - Mannheim-Heidelberg International Filmfestival - Bratislava International Film Festival - Gijon International Film Festival, Spain - Euroshorts Film Festival, Poland - Fest - New Directors New Film, Portugal - Fresh Film Fest, Czech Republic - International Young Filmmakers Festival of Granada, Spain 	
Thematic festivals are festivals that select their films based on certain topics			
Social Concern Festivals are festivals with programming focused on social concerns and/or activism:			
Disability film festivals	Festivals concerned with disability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Eop! Film Festival 	
Environmental and nature	Festivals concerned with environment and nature	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Environmental Film Festival in the USA 	
Human rights	Festivals concerned with human rights	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Amnesty International Film Festival in Japan 	
Mental Health	Festivals concerned with mental health	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Scottish Mental Health and Arts Film Festival 	
Other thematic festivals:			

Science	Festivals that select their films focused on science	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 360 Contemporary Science Film Festival, Russia - Imagine Science Film Festival, USA 	
History	Festivals that select their films around the topic of history and biographies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Biografilm Festival, Italy - Kyoto Historica International Film Festival, Japan - Festival du Film Historique de Waterloo, Belgium 	
Food and wine	Festivals that select their films focused on the topic of food and wine	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Napa Valley Film festival, USA 	
Random themes	Other small themes such as for example trains, horses, etc.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Festival Cinerail, France - Provinciale, Germany - Cine Contracorriente, Colombia - Equus Film Festival, USA 	
Other formats – festivals that reflect shifting logics in film/media consumption and distribution			
TV festivals	Festivals focusing on TV	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cologne Conference International Film and TV Festival 	
Online	Festivals that take place online (before COVID-19)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Goiania Mostra Curtas - Food for Real Film Festival, UK - Tutti Nello Stesso Piatto, Italy 	
Series	Festivals that focus on series	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Miami Web Fest 	
Screenplay	Festivals that feature Screenplays	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Shetlands Film Festival, UK - Projection au Festival des Scenaristes, France 	

Screenings that are not festivals

If the event of a reported film screening is identified as a festival (e.g., instead as a „special screening“, „film series“, etc.), it is coded as “not a festival.” If possible, the event is then categorized further according to the following sub-categories:

- art context
- educational (e.g. screenings at colleges, universities, etc.)
- NGO
- industry initiatives
- cultural institutions
- archives
- repertoire cinemas

5. Indirect Ways to Measure Festival’s “Importance”

One of the main challenges in translating the tier system classification into an empirical study is operationalization and measure of importance of a given festival. The question here is: How can we measure to what extent a given festival matters and what role it plays in the festival circuit? Here it is important to include not only an industry-driven system that is largely based

on external classification such as for example FIAPF accreditation, but also integrate the knowledge of specialized sub-circuits that are also operating on certain logics, be it audience-driven or with a view to other stakeholders. This way, the festival significance can also capture the worth of smaller festivals for exhibition/distribution of films on the network.

Existing industry-driven ranking systems use a tight system that usually excludes smaller festivals and lacks transparency of used criteria. One form of ranking can be exemplified by the qualifying festival lists of the Academy Awards (Academy of Motion Pictures and Sciences) and the British Academy of Film (BAFTA). Both organizations update their lists yearly without providing any clarification on why a certain festival is no longer in the same quality group. The FIAPF (Fédération Internationale des Associations de Producteurs de Films) controversially operates an accreditation system, which endorses 47 film festivals worldwide in four categories: competitive feature film festivals, competitive specialised feature film festivals, non-competitive feature film festivals and documentary and short film festivals. The first two categories are commonly referred to as the ‘A-list’ and ‘B-list’ and are sometimes used as such by film festivals in their marketing. However, this classification scheme was subject to significant criticism both from scholarly and industry observers (Stringer 2016). When accused of unfair ranking for including smaller festivals such as Shanghai in the A-list alongside more established festivals such as Cannes and Venice, the FIAPF has defended its rankings by suggesting, “accredited film festivals are categorised depending on their programming profile, not through some unilateral and subjective criteria about what constitutes quality” (Shackleton 2007).

While the Circulation project collects data on external evaluation (described in section 4), it goes beyond these direct measures of “importance” by attempting two different indirect approaches. In the first instance, we use existing industry lists as a proxy for significance. This has the benefit of making use of in-built expert knowledge that has led to the creation of such lists and their ranking of festivals. We are aware that the underlying arguments behind these lists are neither transparent nor accessible. However, we extend the industry-driven logic of ranking by analyzing a larger collection of festival lists to look for overlaps and co-occurrences of certain festivals. From a research perspective, we attempt to test other models of festival ranking and measure importance of a given festival based on the actual outcomes of festival runs (equivalent to circulation power) as well as connections to other festivals via using a social network analysis.

Importance based on compiled festival lists

Within the Circulation project, we collected lists of film festivals compiled by various institutions and organizations. Such curated lists assisted building a festival library, which can serve as a data source on its own and assist in filling in some of the categories mentioned in Section 4 (e.g., month and location). In addition, they can also serve as a proxy for festivals’ importance, following the logic that if a festival is being “cited” by a significant number of sources it indicates a certain degree of relevance. This way, we aim to include industry logics and insider evaluations of what is considered a significant film festival. The used sources include film funding agencies, especially those who use festivals as a reference point for future funding, like the German National Film Funder FFA (*Filmförderungsanstalt*), or national film institutes and film promotion arms, like German Films, Telefilm Canada, Unifrance, Unijapan, etc. (See Appendix I). We also tried to include lists from various geographical areas (see Figure 6). Top countries of festival locations include:

1. USA - 20 % (of all festivals)
2. UK - 8 % (of all festivals)
3. Spain - 7 % (of all festivals)
4. Germany - 6 % (of all festivals)
5. France - 6 % (of all festivals)
6. Italy - 6 % (of all festivals)
7. Canada - 5 % (of all festivals)
8. Australia - 2% (of all festivals)
9. South Korea - 2% (of all festivals)
10. Poland - 2 % (of all festivals)

Figure 6: Geographical distribution of festivals in the current festival library (data collection and processing are ongoing). Colors correspond to percentages, $n=3.025$.

The resulting library by no means constitutes a representative list (at the global level) of high quality festivals, it merely gives a qualitative hint on which festivals are noticed and acknowledged by relevant actors at international and local levels. The library with the festivals collected from the above-mentioned sources include 3.025 film festivals. Table 8 shows that festivals which were often listed in the above mentioned sources are known and prominent festivals. Thus, this does indeed reflect our hypothesis of a shared knowledge and consensus in the industry.

Table 8. Festivals from the library, mentioned in at least 20 % of the sources

Festival name	% of the sources that cite the festival	FIAPF accreditation of 2018
Berlin international film festival	63	competitive film festival
Cannes international film festival	61	competitive film festival
Locarno international film festival	61	competitive film festival
Venice international film festival	58	competitive film festival
International film festival Rotterdam	55	not accredited
TIFF Toronto international film festival	53	non-competitive film festival
Karlovy Vary international film festival	53	competitive film festival
San Sebastian international film festival	50	competitive film festival
Annecey international animation film festival	47	not accredited

International Documentary film festival Amsterdam (IDFA)	47	not accredited
Hot Docs canadian international documentary festival	42	not accredited
Clermont Ferrand international short film festival	42	not accredited
Sundance film festival	42	not accredited
International short film festival Oberhausen	37	documentary and short film festival
Busan international film festival	37	competitive specialised film festival
Tampere film festival	34	documentary and short film festival
BFI London film festival	34	not accredited
Melbourne international film festival	32	not accredited
DOK Leipzig international Leipzig festival for Documentary and Animated film	32	not accredited
Palm Springs international shortfest	32	not accredited
SXSW film festival	32	not accredited
Tribeca film festival	32	not accredited
Mar del Plata international film festival	29	competitive film festival
Shanghai international film festival	29	competitive film festival
Stuttgart festival of animated film	29	not accredited
Cork film festival	29	not accredited
Guadalajara international film festival	29	not accredited
Warsaw international film festival	29	competitive film festival
Goteborg film festival	29	not accredited
Edinburgh international film festival	29	not accredited
Chicago international film festival	29	not accredited
Sydney film festival	26	competitive specialised film festival
Sarajevo film festival	26	not accredited
Montreal festival du nouveau cinema	26	not accredited
Ottawa international animation festival	26	not accredited
CPH DOX	26	not accredited
Hamburg international short film festival	26	not accredited
Hong Kong international film festival	26	not accredited
Tokyo international film festival	26	competitive film festival
Krakow film festival	26	documentary and short film festival
JIFF Jeonju international film festival	26	not accredited
Sitges international fantastic film festival of catalonia	26	competitive specialised film festival
International film festival Nyon	26	not accredited
BAFICI Buenos Aires international independent film festival	24	not accredited
Sao Paulo international film festival	24	not accredited
Zlin film festival international festival for children and youth	24	not accredited

JFF Jerusalem film festival	24	not accredited
YIDFF Yamagata international documentary film festival	24	not accredited
Moscow international film festival	24	competitive film festival
BIFAN Bucheon international fantastic film festival	24	not accredited
Gijon international film festival	24	competitive specialised film festival
Dubai international film festival	24	not accredited
Encounters film festival	24	not accredited
Leedsfilmfest	24	not accredited
Sheffield doc fest	24	not accredited
Chicago international children's film festival	24	not accredited
Seattle international film festival	24	not accredited
Viennale vienna international film festival	21	non-competitive film festivals
Short film festival Leuven	21	not accredited
Vancouver international film festival	21	not accredited
Animafest Zagreb World festival of animated film	21	not accredited
Jihlava international documentary film festival	21	not accredited
Tallinn Black Nights film festival	21	competitive film festival
Directors Fortnight	21	not accredited
Thessaloniki international film festival	21	not accredited
Giffoni film festival	21	not accredited
Rome film fest	21	not accredited
TFF Torino film festival	21	competitive specialised film festival
Go Short international short film festival nijmegen	21	not accredited
Indie Lisboa - international film festival	21	not accredited
Durban international film festival	21	not accredited
Bilbao international festival of documentary and short films	21	mentary and short film festival
Seminci Valladolid international film festival	21	not accredited
Stockholm international film festival	21	competitive specialised film festival
Uppsala international short film festival	21	not accredited
Kyiv iff molodist	21	competitive specialised film festival
Raindance film festival	21	not accredited
AFI Fest	21	not accredited
Flickers Rhode Island international film festival	21	flickers
NYFF New York film festival	21	not accredited
Telluride film festival	21	not accredited

Modelling attempt: Importance based on interconnections with other festivals in network form

This approach assumes that the “importance” of a festival can be measured based on interconnections with other festivals in network form, where festivals treated as nodes and connections between them are defined via traveling films. Based on a network analysis of films traveling through film festivals, we can visualize the structure of the network’s relationships as well as identified festivals’ positions within the network. Specifically, we can look at usual measures of importance such as centrality measures (Newman 2010) as well as brokerage measures that take into consideration the whole structure of the network (Everett/Valente 2016). The brokerage measures can help identify festivals in a “broker” position (Collins-Dogrul 2012, 991) – i.e., festivals connecting unconnected sub-circuits. In addition, we will attempt to look for festivals with a lot of control over a festival run – in network theory the so called “gatekeepers.” According to Burt’s Structural Holes theory (2005), broker’s control of information and resources implies a possibility of gatekeeping and therefore “a measure of strategic advantage and information control” (Hawe/Ghali 2007, 64). Various characteristics of festivals can be captured via visualization with the help of color, size, shape, and labels. This way, we aim to capture positions and interconnection of various festival sub-circuits.

Film characteristics can be incorporated by comparing the structure of festival networks across different groups of films. For instance, films with theatrical release, longer festival run and a more diverse geographical outreach are likely to have a different network structure coalesced with different network positions.

6. Conclusion and further challenges

The current working paper touched upon possible empirical approaches to translating theoretical classifications of festivals into a quantitative study. In addition to some difficulties discussed above, one of the main challenges here is to correctly capture temporal dimensions. Film festivals change focus, location, date or simply stop existing. Hence, it becomes difficult to evaluate them retrospectively (as many of them do not publish archives or do not preserve web visibility after closure) and collected data can soon become out of date. Therefore, in the long term, questions of sustainable data collection and storage will need more attention.

Another challenge here constitutes data access. Researching detailed information about a large pool of festivals requires a notable number of working hours. Sometimes reported festivals do not have complete information about the date and location and even if they do, they still need to be manually researched and categorized. With a digital humanities perspective, one could think of alternative approaches to manual search of such data. Methodological avenues to further explore would include direct cooperation with festivals and the evaluation of data of digital sources such as festival submission platforms or Wikipedia. Commercial platforms provide a broader look at the festival landscape and allow a fast way to access relevant festival characteristics, such as for example foundation year. Data cooperation with festivals could make it possible to collect high quality data on industry networks and markets, which otherwise are not easily available.

Literature

- “Academy of Motion Pictures and Sciences.” n.d. Accessed May 16, 2021.
<https://www.oscars.org>.
- Baptist, Vincent. 2018. “Pilot Study on the Dutch Film Festival Landscape 2017: Research Internship Report.”
- “British Academy of Film and Television Arts.” n.d. Accessed May 16, 2021.
<https://www.bafta.org>.
- Burt, Ronald S. n.d. “Reinforced Structural Holes.” *Social Networks* 43: 149–61.
- Callegaro, Mario, Katja Lozar Manfreda, and Vasja Vehovar, ‘Relation Between Nonresponse Rates and Nonresponse Biases’, in *Web Survey Methodology* (London: Sage, 2015), p. 344 <<https://study.sagepub.com/web-survey-methodology>>
- Campos-Rabadán, Minerva. 2020. “Tensiones En El Circuito Cinematográfico Internacional: Modelo Para El Estudio De Los Festivales Latinoamericanos.” *Comunicación y Medios*, no. 42: 72–84. <https://doi.org/10.5354/0719-1529.2020.57224>.
- Collins-Dogrul, Julie. 2012. “Tertius Iungens Brokerage and Transnational Intersectoral Cooperation.” *Organization Studies* 33 (8): 989–1014.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0170840612445118>.
- Colta, Alexandra-Maria. 2019. “Politics and Programming Practices at Human Rights Film Festivals: A Study of Document Human Rights Film Festival.” PhD Thesis, School of Culture and Creative Arts, College of Arts, University of Glasgow.
- de Valck, Marijke. 2007. *Film Festivals: From European Geopolitics to Global Cinephilia*. Amsterdam: Amsterdam University Press.
- de Valck, Marijke. 2014. “Supporting Art Cinema at a Time of Commercialization: Principles and Practices, the Case of the International Film Festival Rotterdam.” *Poetics*, no. 42: 40–59. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.poetic.2013.11.004>.
- de Valck, Marijke, and Skadi Loist. 2009. “Film Festival Studies: An Overview of a Burgeoning Field.” In *Film Festival Yearbook 1: The Festival Circuit*, edited by Dina Iordanova and Ragan Rhyne, 179–215. St. Andrews: St Andrews Film Studies.
- Dovey, Lindiwe. 2015. *Curating Africa in the Age of Film Festivals: Film Festivals, Time, Resistance*. Framing Film Festivals. London, New York: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Elsaesser, Thomas. 2005. “Film Festival Networks: The New Topographies of Cinema in Europe.” In *European Cinema: Face to Face with Hollywood*, 82–107. Amsterdam: Amsterdam University Press.
- Everett, Martin G., and Thomas W. Valente. 2016. “Bridging, Brokerage and Betweenness.” *Social Networks* 44 (January): 202–8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socnet.2015.09.001>.
- “Fédération Internationale Des Associations de Producteurs de Films.” n.d. Accessed May 16, 2021. <http://www.fiapf.org>.
- Grove, Elliott. “5 Types of Festivals: A Classification.” fest21.com, 10 Apr. 2009, www.fest21.com/en/blog/editor/5_types_of_festivals_a_classification_by_elliott_grove. Accessed 27 May 2011.
- Groves, Robert M., ‘Three Eras of Survey Research’, *Public Opinion Quarterly*, 75.5 (2011), 861–71 <<https://doi.org/10.1093/poq/nfr057>>
- Hawe, Penelope, and Laura Ghali. 2008. “Use of Social Network Analysis to Map the Social Relationships of Staff and Teachers at School.” *Health Education Research* 23 (1): 62–69. <https://doi.org/10.1093/her/cyl162>.
- Iordanova, Dina, and Ruby Cheung, editors. *Film Festival Yearbook 2: Film Festivals and Imagined Communities*. St Andrews Film Studies, 2010.
- Iordanova, Dina, and Ruby Cheung, editors. *Film Festival Yearbook 3: Film Festivals and East Asia*. St Andrews Film Studies, 2011.

- Iordanova, Dina, and Leshu Torchin, editors. *Film Festival Yearbook 4: Film Festivals and Activism*. St Andrews Film Studies, 2012.
- Iordanova, Dina, and Stefanie Van de Peer, editors. *Film Festival Yearbook 6: Film Festivals and the Middle East*. St Andrews Film Studies, 2014.
- “Jewish Film Festivals in 2019.” Accessed May 14, 2021.
<https://jewishfilmfestivals.org/festivals/in-2019/>.
- Krainhöfer, Tanja C. 2018. “Der Deutsche Festivalmarkt: The German Festival Market.” *Blickpunkt:Film Fokus:Festivals* (1): 28–32.
- Loist, Skadi. 2014. “Rêves transversaux: La circulation des films *queer* dans le réseau des festivals.” Transl. Brigitte Rollet. *Diogène*, no. 245: 80–103.
<https://doi.org/10.3917/dio.245.0080>.
- Loist, Skadi. 2016. “The Film Festival Circuit: Networks, Hierarchies, and Circulation.” In *Film Festivals: History, Theory, Method, Practice*, edited by Marijke de Valck, Brendan Kredell, and Skadi Loist, 49–64. London, New York: Routledge.
- Loist, Skadi. 2018a. “Crossover Dreams: Global Circulation of Queer Film on the Film Festival Circuits.” *Diogenes* 62 (1): 57–72. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0392192116667014>.
- Loist, Skadi. 2018b. “Queer Film Festivals Globally (1977-2017).” Google map. Accessed January 25, 2018. <http://tinyurl.com/yaq8d3cf>.
- Loist, Skadi. 2020. “Zirkulation im Netzwerk: Eine Betrachtung zur Zirkulationskraft von Filmfestivals.” *Zeitschrift für Medienwissenschaft*, no. 23: 55-63.
<https://doi.org/10.25969/mediarep/14833>.
- Loist, Skadi, and Marijke de Valck. 2019. “FFRN Bibliography.” Accessed October 15, 2020. <http://www.filmfestivalresearch.org/index.php/ffrn-bibliography/>.
- Loist, Skadi, and Zhenya Samoilova. 2020. “First Results from Our Survey of Filmmakers on How Their Films Traveled Through Festivals.” *Film Circulation*, January 9, 2020.
<http://www.filmcirculation.net/2020/01/09/first-results-from-our-survey-of-filmmakers-on-how-their-films-traveled-through-festivals/>.
- Loist, Skadi, and Ann Vogel. 2014. “Teddy Film Study.” Pilot study for film circulation.
- Loist, Skadi, and Ger Zielinski. 2012. “On the Development of Queer Film Festivals and Their Media Activism.” In *Film Festival Yearbook 4: Film Festivals and Activism*, edited by Dina Iordanova and Leshu Torchin, 49–62. St Andrews: St Andrews Film Studies.
- Newman, Mark. 2010. “Measures and Metrics.” In *Networks: An Introduction*, 158–217. Oxford University Press.
- Peirano, María Paz. 2016. “Pursuing, Resembling, and Contesting the Global: The Emergence of Chilean Film Festivals.” *New Review of Film and Television Studies* 14 (1): 112–31. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17400309.2015.1109345>.
- Peirano, María Paz, and Sebastián González Itier. 2018. *Los Festivales De Cine En Chile (1967-2018)*. Informe Festivales de Cine en Chile: ventanas de exhibición y difusión del cine chileno. Accessed May 15, 2021. www.festivalesdecine.cl.
- Samoilova, Zhenya, and Skadi Loist, ‘Film Circulation Project Questionnaire’, 2019
<<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3581359>>
- Shackleton, Liz. “FIAPF Defends Film Festival Accreditation System.” *Screen Daily*, 9 July 2007, www.screendaily.com/fiapf-defends-film-festival-accreditation-system/4033493.article. Accessed 10 May 2021.
- Taillibert, Christel. 2009. *Tribulations festivalières: Les festivals de cinéma et audiovisuel en France*. Logiques sociales. Études culturelles. Paris: Harmattan.
- Vallejo, Aida. 2012. “Festivales de cine documental: Redes de circulación cultural en el este del continente europeo. (Documentary Film Festivals: Networks of Cultural Circulation

- in the Eastern Part of Europe).” PhD Thesis, Facultad de Filosofía y Letras, Universidad Autónoma de Madrid.
- Vallejo, Aida. 2014. “Industry Sections: Documentary Film Festivals Between Production and Distribution.” *Illuminace* 26 (1): 65–81.
<http://www.iluminace.cz/index.php/en/article?id=179>. Accessed March 05, 2020.
- van Vliet, Harry. *Festival Atlas 2017: Film Festivals*. Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences.
- Zachar, Gerald, and Michael Paul. 2016. “Filmfestivalreport Österreich. Zur Situation Der Österreichischen Filmfestivals: Finanzierung, Effekte & Strategische Aussichten.”.

Appendix I

1. German Films, as of 2019
2. FFA (German funding institution FFA) as of 2019
3. Telefilm Canada as of 2019 (<https://telefilm.ca/en/festivals-markets/festival-circuit>)
4. Unifrance as of 2019 (<https://en.unifrance.org/festivals-and-markets>)
5. Unijapan as of 2019 (<https://www.unijapan.org/english/news/awards/>)
6. Film Institute Netherlands as of 2019
(https://international.eyefilm.nl/Festivals_Markets.html)
7. Ministry of Education, Spain, as of 2019 (<http://www.culturaydeporte.gob.es/cultura-mecd/en/areas-cultura/cine/promocion/festivales-cinematograficos.html>)
8. British Council as of 2019 (<http://film.britishcouncil.org/festivals-directory>)
9. Film Commission Poland as of 2019 (<http://filmcommissionpoland.pl/film-industry/film-events-calendar/>)
10. Arab Cinema Center as of 2019, including film institutes of Lebanon, Egypt, Qatar, Morocco, Palestine, Tunisia, Oman, Saudi Arabia, Jordan (<http://acc.film/festival-markets.php>)
11. Screen Australia as of 2019 (<https://www.screenaustralia.gov.au/festivals-and-markets/festival-profiles>)
12. Bulgarian National Film Center as of 2019 (<http://www.old.nfc.bg/festivals/others>)
13. Cinema Chile as of 2019 (<http://www.cinemachile.cl/en/festivales/>)
14. Creative Europe Media as of 2019 (<https://www.coe.int/en/web/eurimages/eurimages-prize-list>)
15. European Film Academy as of 2019
(<https://www.europeanfilmacademy.org/Links.38.0.html>)
16. Eurimages as of 2019 (<https://www.coe.int/en/web/eurimages/eurimages-prize-list>)
17. European Film Promotion as of 2019 (https://www.efp-online.com/en/events_initiatives.php
https://www.efp-online.com/en/events_initiatives.php)
18. Greek Film Center as of 2019
(<http://webcache.googleusercontent.com/search?q=cache:http://www.gfc.gr/en/info-center/film-festivals-in-greece.html>)
19. Filmitalia as of 2019 (<http://www.filmitalia.org/p.aspx?t=festivalshome&l=en>)
20. Israel film fund as of 2019 (http://intl.filmfund.org.il/industry_guide/)
21. Screen Ireland as of 2019 (<https://www.screenireland.ie/promoting>)
22. Proimágenes Colombia as of 2019
(<http://www.proimagenescolombia.com/secciones/eventos/eventos.php?tipo=2>)
23. Austrian Film Institute as of 2019 (<https://www.imcine.gob.mx/estimulos-y-apoyos/convocatorias>)
24. Film fund Luxembourg as of 2019 (<http://www.filmfund.lu/t/links>)
25. Swiss films as of 2019
(http://www.swissfilms.ch/de/festivals_long_films/festival_agenda/)
26. Korean Film Council as of 2019
(<http://www.koreanfilm.or.kr/eng/coProduction/festivalList.jsp>)
27. Czech Film Center as of 2019 (<https://www.filmcenter.cz/en/czech-film-industry/film-festivals>)
28. Magyar Hungary as of 2019
(http://filmunio.eu/index.php?option=com_wrapper&view=wrapper&id=91&Itemid=64&lang=en)
29. BAFTA as of 2018

30. Academy Awards as of 2018
31. Teddy award pilot study 2014-2016 on films listed in the Teddy Awards film catalogue of the Berlinale (Loist & Vogel)
32. Festivals listings in Dovey (2015)
33. Listing of African film festivals provided by Lara Utian-Preston
34. Human rights festivals listing in Colta 2019
35. Festival listings in Iordanova/Cheung 2010
36. Festival listings in Iordanova/Cheung 2011 (Asian film festivals)
37. Festival listings in Iordanova/Torchin 2012 (activist film festivals)
38. Festival listings in Marlow-Mann 2013 (archival film festivals)
39. Festival listings in Iordanova/Van de Peer 2014 (festivals in the MENA region)
40. Jewishfilmfestivals.org (2019)